

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF COMBINING TRADITIONAL AND INTEGRATIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING PROFESSIONAL-ORIENTED ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article discusses the relevance of an integrated approach to studying a specialized foreign language within the framework of the basic vocational education program. It is emphasized that learning a foreign language requires studying the culture of another nation and this is, in fact, one of the main reasons for studying languages, which means getting acquainted with the culture of other nations and countries, the worldview of different people. It is noted that as the number of languages studied increases, people's worldview expands and they become stronger and more developed. The main properties of the most frequently used traditional and interactive methods of teaching a foreign language are considered. From the analysis of various theoretical and methodological approaches in pedagogical research and the experiences of many leading researchers in the world, it was revealed that the most effective and appropriate is the methodological approach that leads to the integration of traditional and interactive methods.

Keywords: Integrated approach, oral speech, competence, method, traditional, interactive.

Introduction

Modern achievements in the field of science and technology, coupled with emerging competition on a global scale, have a significant impact on the behavior of young people regarding the promotion of the idea that “a person must be successful” in all spheres of human life. Becoming a specialist after completing various training courses and obtaining a new status does not always mean acquiring new knowledge, skills and qualifications. This trend can be seen even in the field of higher education, that is, receiving a certificate or diploma upon completion of training only means having a document, but does not guarantee that a person has specific skills in this area or his growth in future professional activities.

Today, in higher educational institutions specializing in the field of journalism, there are such common problems as lack of motivation of students to study foreign languages, their lack of desire to master educational material, and inability to make sufficient progress in educational activities. Therefore, one of the important tasks of modern higher education is the formation of a spiritually and intellectually developed personality, striving to be enriched with the values of local and foreign culture, as well as expanding the circle of communication through professional communication with representatives of different cultures. The priority task of students should be the development of mental abilities and the desire not for success only as a status, but for understanding their value to society, for knowledge, respect and veneration of traditions, for preserving the cultural heritage of different nationalities [1]. And the task of a modern teacher in this aspect is very broad and important, because in our time the need to attract the attention and interest of young people is sometimes a difficult task even for the most experienced specialists.

Language teachers always emphasize that learning a foreign language requires learning the culture of another nation. This is, in fact, one of the main reasons for learning languages, which means experiencing the inner culture of another country, learning the worldview of different people and enriching the ability to appreciate different experiences. Language learning and culture cannot be separated, and therefore learning culture and language together is the most effective and successful [2].

There is a saying among people in my nation: “One language-one person”, that is, a person who knows one language knows one nation, and a person who knows two languages knows two nations together with their culture, traditions and life style. As the number of languages increases, the person learning them becomes stronger and develops, as well as his worldview expands. People who know different languages can look at things from different angles. Learning a language, of course, requires a good knowledge of vocabulary and syntax. But language teachers sometimes neglect the importance of teaching culture, so the potential of language learning to create cultural understanding is not realized.

It should be noted that the acquisition of basic competencies, including socio-political, communication, information, sociocultural knowledge, skills and qualifications, modern information has become the main goal of personal education in accordance with the requirements of a multicultural world [3]. Among these competencies, the communicative competence of a foreign language is systemic and fundamental for all subjects, since the process of teaching a foreign language organically combines the formation of all other competencies in its development. This is not only a goal, but also a means of effective personal development. Thus, learning a foreign language enriches a person with new

knowledge and helps expand his worldview. This is a source of topics for communication, including topics in a foreign language, which is not without diplomacy and even simplifies the search for common ground for a sincere and effective communication process.

Features of some traditional and interactive methods of teaching a foreign language

The relevance of studying a specialized foreign language within the framework of the basic professional education program for various areas of training future journalists is associated with the need to work with primary sources in a foreign language. Also in formal and informal conditions, in everyday and sociocultural communication, it manifests itself in the implementation of oral communication with representatives of other cultures and nationalities in a foreign language, formal and informal provision of communication, and an adequate response to the characteristics of the interlocutor's oral speech.

The most commonly used traditional approaches to teaching foreign language include grammatical translation, audiolingual approach, direct method, structured approach, task-based language learning, team approach, communicative approach and ESL (English as a secondary language).

There are several effective methods of teaching a foreign language, one of which is teaching a foreign language through grammatical translation. This method has been the only and important part of teaching a foreign language in our country for many years. As a result of the emergence of the communicative method and its subsequent widespread dissemination, teaching a foreign language through translation has become a "traditional" method. But other similar methods, many teaching tools characteristic of communicative activities, have remained as successful teaching methods. When teaching a foreign language through translation, certain results can be achieved by comprehensively practicing these skills, using language as a means of oral and written communication.

The translation method mainly exists in two forms: the grammatical translation method and the text translation method. From the point of view of this method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammar exercises are performed with the aim of developing the logical thinking of the language learner. According to the method, systematic grammatical theory occupies the main place in the content of teaching a foreign language [4].

Using grammatical translation method, the student first learns material in the target language, translating it into his native language. Teachers encourage students to memorize grammar rules and vocabulary. It is important to note that speaking and listening are more or less oriented towards the use of this method. When teachers use this method, they conduct classes in their native language.

In the modern educational process, the method of grammatical translation is used in combination with a communicative approach, which has a relatively good effect on the development of students' oral speech

competence. As a result, students have increasing opportunities to transform themselves from foreign language learners into accomplished language users.

The structural approach, which is considered a traditional approach, studies the various units of language such as sounds, morphemes, words, sentences and vocabulary [5]. It also facilitates the process of learning a language based on grammatical structures [6]. An example of this is first teaching the verb "to be" and then teaching the present continuous tense, where "to be" is used as an auxiliary verb. That is, easy-to-understand grammatical concepts are taught earlier than more complex ones. This approach teaches the four basic language skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing. Teachers can use this technique with many other language teaching methods.

Using the task-based language learning method, students perform real-life tasks using the foreign languages they are learning. In this case, preference is given to fluency in each task completed by the student. Direct error correction has been reduced to increase students' self-confidence.

In the task-based approach to language teaching, tasks are divided into three categories:

- An information gap or task in which information must be transferred from one person, place, or form to another.

- Tasks related to information range that require the learner to discover new knowledge from a given set of information through reasoning, deduction, perception and inference.

- Thought range tasks where students complete a task, expressing their thoughts and feelings about a specific situation.

Activities that can be used in problem-based learning include presentations on a topic assigned in class and conversations with peers or adults in the target language, debates, discussions, newspaper creation, and a short presentation on current events. With this approach, students are given some freedom to explore the language they want to learn. And the teacher usually acts as an observer or instructor [7]. At the same time, learners can also develop self-reflection and teamwork skills.

In the method of learning a foreign language based on collective approach, the audience is perceived as a single whole. Together they learn foreign language skills through practical interaction with each other. In this teaching method, the teacher acts more as an instructor or guide than as a speaker. In general, there is no specific selected activity during the lesson. Instead, students decide what they want to talk about. They sit in a circle and decide what to talk about. But during a conversation, they may ask the teacher for advice on how to translate or pronounce a sentence or idea or how to say something. All conversations are recorded and then transcribed. Students and teacher can analyze grammar and vocabulary as well as content related to the topic.

Another feature of the collective approach method is language exchange, which is used in some bilingual education programs. When switching languages, the message is presented first in your native language and

then in the foreign language you are studying. Students learn the meaning of the words by memorizing parallel meanings in their native language. They summarize the contents of this set of messages. Using this method during training, a student volunteer presents a message to a pre-selected "expert" in his native language. The "expert" translates the message into a foreign language. The student then repeats the message in a foreign language and addresses another student who wants to communicate with him. Although language learning with this method does not fully cover the English language, students learn what they want to learn. Students also play a major role in these activities whenever possible.

Famous methodological researchers, such as Galskova N.D. and Gez N.I., Bim I.L., Passov E.I. and others have developed a communicative approach to teaching foreign languages, emphasizing interactive methods as one of the promising teaching tools [8; 9; 10].

Communicative language teaching can be understood as a set of principles concerning the goals of language teaching, how students learn language, the types of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and students during learning [11]. This approach is one of the interactive teaching methods, the effective use of which makes it possible to turn the student into an active participant in the pedagogical process, to form and develop the student's cognitive activity. The use of interactive methods helps to develop a creative, active personality capable of changing in a developing world.

Thus, in the methodology of communicative teaching of a foreign language, communication performs the functions of training, cognition, development and education as one of the leading types of human activity. In this case, communication serves as:

- 1) source of knowledge;
- 2) a means of individual development;
- 3) a means of developing the necessary personality qualities;
- 4) a way to gain experience and develop interpersonal skills.

Classes organized on the basis of a communicative approach are personality-oriented, and in the process of communication in the lesson, the direct activities of students, their experience, worldview, academic and extracurricular interests and inclinations, and emotions are taken into account [12]. In this case, the activity is based on discussing current life problems, and not on going through topics or studying ready-made texts. At the same time, students will have the opportunity to discuss current events in the life of the audience, the university, the life of the city, the country, and justify and defend their work and actions.

In the process of learning with a communicative approach, students master methods of communication, learn the rules of speech etiquette, strategies and tactics of dialogue and group communication, learn to solve various communicative problems, and become interlocutors in the speech process. The development of thinking in communicative learning is carried out not

by comparison with the native language, but by solving increasingly complex verbal and mental tasks that reflect the content of the communication process [13;14]. As a result, students develop the cognitive and communicative function of communication.

Discussion or debate from interactive teaching methods: debates and discussions on current topics to develop critical thinking and speaking skills, role-playing games and simulations: the use of role-playing games to simulate professional situations and practicing language in real contexts facilitate the achievement of the goal in the educational process.

In this case, multimedia from educational technologies can be used to improve the perception and production of speech: video, audio and other multimedia resources. It is important to use online resources, online platforms and applications for self-study and communication with native English speakers.

Integrative approach to teaching a foreign language

The study of various theoretical and methodological approaches in pedagogical research, the experience of foreign countries and the countries of the former CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) shows us that the most convenient, logical and expedient integrative approach is a methodological approach that leads to the integration of traditional and interactive methods.

The concept of a system covers mainly the object form of the whole, and the concept of integration covers a process. A complex is a collection of objects, actions, properties or events that are interconnected and form a single whole. And integration means combining parts that are not similar to each other. This preliminary stage of comparison, without going deeply into the descriptive features of each pedagogical approach, allows us to imagine that the essence of integration is wider and deeper than the other two. This creates difficulties, on the one hand, in considering all components and presenting many aspects, and on the other hand, in choosing and taking into account more effective, diverse means and methods in the educational process.

It should be noted that interdisciplinary integration has become widespread and popular in various pedagogical studies, however, the results in this area need further experimental confirmation, since its internal basis and content is the integrity of the educational process. The implementation of an integrative approach involves understanding all four skills of speech and vocabulary with grammar, their essence [15].

Taking into account domestic and foreign experience in foreign language teaching methods, we can distinguish three main approaches to professional - oriented teaching of a foreign language [16;17;18]. Of these:

- 1) foreign language for specific purposes;
- 2) subject-language integrated education;
- 3) teaching specialized subjects in a foreign language.

ESP (English for specific purposes) approach is actively used in the traditional system of teaching a foreign language at a university, the goal of which is the formation of professional linguistic competence. It consists of mastering the grammatical means of professional speech, special vocabulary and vocabulary. The subject of study is a foreign language, which is mainly taught for the purpose of mastering professional vocabulary and speech expression in the professional field [19].

The implementation of an integrative approach to interaction in the educational process involves the use of various pedagogical methods (for example, the project method), interpersonal interaction of students, the development of communication skills, cooperation, co-creation, and the acquisition of skills in finding a balance in human relationships [20]. This, in turn, teaches communication skills and contributes to positive experiences of intercultural interaction [21]. Maintaining cultural connections at a high level requires a re-evaluation of intercultural connections and cultural identity based on the ideas of intercultural tolerance, understanding of cultural differences and acceptance of communication as equal.

Thus, English for specific purposes is taught in universities in our country, taking into account the specific needs of various specialties and socio-economic requirements.

Therefore, particular attention should be given to developing a variety of English language and practical skills to help students achieve better results both academically and in the workplace. For example, English language learners must learn to decode and comprehend certain types of English texts by completing reading comprehension tasks. However, although the integrative approach to foreign language teaching is widely used in some developed countries, in our country it is still at the implementation stage. This is a natural phenomenon because any new approach to higher education will inevitably face problems during the creation phase. Therefore, it is important to determine the basis on which specialists conducting research in this direction will be guided.

In the process of teaching English for specific purposes, it is necessary to pay attention to the following procedures of the assessment and control process:

- Formative assessment: regular feedback and assessment of student performance through tests, questionnaires and oral examinations.
- Summative assessment: final assessment of students' knowledge and skills through exams, public speaking and project defense.

The development of students' oral speech competence in the process of teaching English for specific purposes requires the integration of theoretical and methodological foundations that ensure the successful development of communication skills in a foreign language.

Focusing on the theoretical foundations of the theory of linguistics:

- phonetics: study of the sound system of the English language, correct pronunciation and intonation;

- vocabulary: study of a wide range of vocabulary, including terms and expressions specific to the professional field;

- grammar: mastering grammatical structures necessary for clear and grammatically correct expression of thoughts.

Focusing on psycholinguistic foundations:

- psychological aspects of language acquisition: understanding the mechanisms of speech perception and production, the role of memory and cognitive processes in learning;

- motivational-emotional factor: it is important to take into account the influence of motivation, confidence and emotional state on the success of language acquisition.

If we look at the basics of communication theory:

- communicative approach: focusing on the functional aspects of language, using language for real communication, modeling communication situations;

- interactivity: interaction between students should be recognized, active participation in dialogues and discussions to develop speaking skills.

As a methodological basis, it is permissible to list the following:

- project-oriented approach: projects and presentations, development and presentation of projects in the major in English.

- research activities: performing research assignments and writing scientific articles in English.

Conclusion

Thus, it turns out that the targeted use of an integrative approach in the educational process can significantly increase the effectiveness of teaching English at a university. The successful development of students' oral speech competence during profile-oriented teaching of English language requires an integrated approach, including theoretical and methodological aspects. The combination of linguistic, psycholinguistic and communication theories with innovative teaching methods and technologies makes it possible to create favorable conditions for the formation and improvement of speech skills necessary for professional and educational activities.

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